

Chowndolo

Obstruction Manual

A snapshot

The following pages provide a snapshot of the Chowndolo, an overview at a specific moment in time, merging elements from its various versions, without providing too many details. This is not a step-by-step guide for replication, but rather a prompt for reinterpretation. Think of it as an open score, an inverted instruction booklet or a destruction manual that embraces undoing as much as making. Its purpose is to nurture new mutations, each with its own inheritances, recombinations, and quirks.

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How It Swings?

The instrument employs the pendulum's motion to drive digital sound synthesis in real time. The pendulum has at its end a coil attached to a magnet. To interact with the instrument, the performer arranges magnetic tiles on the base beneath the pendulum, causing it to oscillate and inducing subtle variations in electrical current. This analog signal is amplified with a custom circuit and converted into a digital signal and mapped to control sound synthesis with the Bela microcontroller. To listen to the Chowndolo, it is necessary to plug headphones or speakers to the Bela board.

Arm on a base

The main structure consists of two components: a suspension arm, which holds the pendulum, and a base that supports an array of magnets. The arm is composed of two parts held together by interlocking components. These include two V-shaped elements, which also support the PCB, and two bridges that guide the electrical wiring. The arm attaches to the base through two slits and is locked in place by the tension created when the V-shaped elements are inserted.

Tiles

Key elements of the Chowndolo are its magnetic tiles. Based on Penrose tiling, an aperiodic pattern derived from the golden ratio, they function as an open intuitive score to be arranged underneath the pendulum. Tiles are usually 6mm high with 3mm circular holes. As each tile embeds a magnet, their configuration will alter the pendulum's oscillation. Despite lacking periodicity, the visual pattern maintains a cohesive aesthetic, and with time and practice, one begins to recognise arrangements that induce consistent swings.

The Pendulum

Sensitive to subtle magnetic shifts produced by the tiles below, the pendulum acts as both performer and listener, dancing through unstable trajectories that are eventually translated into sound. Crucial to the instrument's responsiveness is the distance between the coil and the base. The coil enclosure protects the component from damage caused by the snapping of magnets and is attached to a ring magnet which, being attracted or repelled by the tiles, sets the pendulum in motion. A brass tube inserted into the ring magnet limits vertical oscillations and carries the electrical wire that connects the coil to the PCB.

a - Magnetic tile: **b** - Coil enclosure: **c** - Ring magnet: **d** - Brass tube: **e** - 2 core electrical wire: **f** - Stereo 3.5mm jack plug (optional)

Electronics (ie. PCB -> Bela -> Pd -> FM synth -> Joy)

The electric signal coming from the Pendulum is amplified through a custom printed circuit board (PCB). The PCB features two inputs, the pendulum's mini jack and USB power socket, and two output pins which go to Bela, respectively to a ground pin and to the analog input pin A7. Do not forget that Bela also needs to be supplied with power via USB. Once everything is connected and powered, the system should produce sound after approximately 45 seconds, allowing time for Bela to boot. Bela's audio outputs can be routed to speakers or headphones. The sound generated by the Bela platform is defined by a Pure Data (PD) patch that is flashed onto the board. The patch is based on FM synthesis.

The Pd implementation of FM synth for the Chowndolo. FM can generate complex sounds by modulating the frequency of one waveform (the carrier) with another (the modulator). FM is computationally efficient, allowing rich and dynamic timbres to be produced with minimal processing resources.

Phenomenology of a Chowndolo

The Chowndolo lives between a digital instrument and an interactive sculpture. In essence, it is a sounding device built around a magnetic pendulum. The instrument is played by arranging magnetic tiles beneath the pendulum and altering its trajectory. The pendulum's unstable swings are continuously transformed into sound. As if guided by invisible hands, the Chowndolo channels the magic of magnetism, weaving a perpetual interaction, a shifting composition, where chaos and structure disrupt and entwine.

The Chowndolo is an exploration of perception, making tangible the intangible. The installation invites to actively experience sound as an emergent physical phenomenon, by rearranging elements and translating motion into an organic musical experience. The pendulum, traditionally a symbol of time measurement, is remediated as a generator of unpredictable musical time, an inverted metronome dancing with hidden forces. Rooted in media archaeology and sound art practices, the Chowndolo reinterprets past technologies to shape contemporary artistic expression

Version 1
The "franciscan" prototype.
Foldable, raw and agile, born for live performance.

Version 2:
A "gourmette" iteration shaped for a sustainable small-scale production.

Version 3:
A "tank-like" Chowndolo designed to withstand long-term public exhibitions.

Some Background

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The name Chowndolo (from the Italian ciondolo, meaning "swinging pendant") pays tribute to John Chowning, a pioneer of electronic composition and voice synthesis. The instrument generates sound through FM audio synthesis, the technique discovered by Chowning in 1967. When considered structurally, the Chowndolo draws on Modernist influences, such as Gaudí's Floreal Style, as well as the organisation of natural forms, echoing the structural logic found in canopies. The Chowndolo has been performed / presented in many venues including IRCAM Forum (Paris - FR), Barbican Centre (London - UK), Sonar+D (Barcelona - SP), Ars Electronica (Linz - AU), conference of New Interfaces for Musical Expression (Porto Alegre - BR), Maker Faire (Shenzhen - CN) and won the third price at The Guthman Musical Instrument Competition (Atlanta - US).

Through the years, different versions of the Chowndolo have been developed to accommodate different settings and audiences. The original version, a sort of side-project emerged from the research carried out at the Augmented Instruments Lab, was conceived as an agile, fully foldable device for live music settings. It is rooted in a minimal and rough "Franciscan" aesthetic, yet elegant and delicate, highly responsive during interaction. A second version was conceived as part of a broader investigation on sustainable digital instrument design practices to fit a small-scale production and maximize its lifespan. A second version has been developed with the support of the Intelligent Instrument Lab to withstand long-term public exhibitions: sturdy and plug-and-play, this design is built to endure hundreds of users requiring no (or minimal) maintenance.

The research behind the artwork embraces an open-source mindset, prioritising accessibility and repair. We rely on open tools and formats such as Pd for sound synthesis, vector-based file for fabrication, and Kicad for electrical schematics. We provide open access to all core resources, including code, schematics, and 2D/3D design files. We strive for an instrument that remains adaptable and reproducible.

Wanna know more?

What's Pure Data?

Pure Data (PD) is an open-source, visual programming language: instead of traditional code, uses graphical "patches" where sound processes are represented as interconnected objects. You can easily upload a Pd patch on Bela: Just connect the board to your computer with a USB cable, boot up, and access the Bela IDE by navigating to bela.local/ in a web browser (Chrome recommended).

To know more about Pd visit puredata.info

What is Bela?

Bela is a platform designed for crafting responsive, sensor-based, interactive audio systems. It is possible to programme Bela using various languages, including C++. For the Chowndolo we use Pure Data (Pd), a programming language for real-time audio processing. Once powered, Bela automatically loads a Pd programme. The programme reads the incoming voltage and uses it to control the parameters of frequency modulation (FM) synth.

To know more about Bela visit learn.bela.io

Troubleshooting

No sound?

Check all the connections and make sure the Bela is running (blue blinks). Remember to wait a little after powering the circuit (2 USB cables).

Debugging

In the "Pd\Test" folder you will find two diagnostic patches: AudioTest verifies your audio output is working correctly, while InputTest displays the coil's incoming signal on an oscilloscope for visual inspection. Use these to identify hardware or software issues. Scan the QR code to access the patches.

Credits:

version 1:

Concept & Sound: Giacomo Lepri
Design: Giacomo Lepri & Alessia Milo
With the support of Augmented Instruments Laboratory

version 2:

Concept & Sound: Giacomo Lepri
Design: Giacomo Lepri & Nicolò Merendino (aka "Chi ha ucciso Il Conte?")
With the support of Augmented Instruments Laboratory & Centro Sonologia Computazionale

version 3:

Concept & Sound: Giacomo Lepri
Design: Giacomo Lepri & Halldór Úlfarsson
With the support of Augmented Instruments Laboratory & Intelligent Instruments Laboratory.

Manual design: Nicolò Merendino (aka "Chi ha Ucciso Il Conte?") and Giacomo Lepri
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